

Mokhtar R. Haman: A dedication to his memory

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It is with more sorrow and tremendous sadness we remember the death of our colleague the Libyan pharmacist, professor **Mokhtar Ramadan Haman**, at his home in Tripoli, Libya after long-suffering from brain cancer. He died on 02, February 2017 and his immaculate corpse was buried on the following day at the Souk-Al-Ahad cemetery, Bin Ghashir Palace. Professor Haman (Photo 1), was born in Tripoli, Libya, on January 1, 1957. He obtained his Bachelor of Pharmaceutical Sciences in 1981 at the University of Tripoli and his Ph.D. in Pharmacognosy in 1989 at Cardiff University, UK.

Photo 1: Professor Mokhtar R. Haman

Prof. Haman devoted his scientific life to the exploration of Arab Medicinal Flora, traditional medicinal plants, and their use in Libya and North Africa and he became the leading scientist in Pharmacognosy and complementary and alternative medicine in Libya. His students remember him as an inspiring teacher and perceptive critic with a precise, ironic sense of humor tempered by gentle kindness.

Prof. Haman held several positions in his life including the head of the scientific committee and the director of the postgraduate studies office at the Faculty of

Pharmacy, University of Tripoli. He was a member of the supreme committee for alternative medicine, Ministry of Health, Libya; a chairman of the alternative medicine committee in Tripoli, Libya; a member of the Arab Committee for Arab Medical Fluorosis; a member of the organization of Mediterranean Countries (EUROMID) for medicinal drugs; a member of the committee preparing the evaluation guide for university education institutions in Libya affiliated to the Quality Assurance Center in the educational institutions of the Ministries of Education, Higher Education and Scientific Research; a member of the technical subcommittee of the Graduate Studies Program, University of Tripoli; and the Chairman of the Committee for follow-up of research projects at the National Authority for Scientific Research. He also participated in many inspection visits and audits of pharmaceutical companies in many countries as well as in audit visits to educational institutions by the Quality Assurance Center.

Prof. Haman was one of the intellectual leaders of the Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Tripoli, and a source of inspiration and leadership to young teachers and researchers entering the field of medicinal plants. Haman's scientific contributions in the field of Pharmacognosy were many in numbers and diversity [1, 2].

The aspect of his personality was not only reflected in his work but also characterized his personal interactions at meetings of scientific and administration throughout the university. His unique style generated enthusiastic and light-hearted discussions, and will greatly be missed. Although his daily involvement in the direction of his Faculty, in teaching and research, would have easily been enough for most of us. Haman always found the

energy to create plans to develop phytochemistry research programs for researchers in many scientific centers in Libya. He was deeply aware of the evanescent nature of life, happiness, and human potential. His departure has left us in great sorrow and dismay. It was too soon for him to leave and we can hardly grasp his decision to depart from life and the love of family and friends. Prof Haman will never be forgotten and mourn his loss as a beloved colleague and friend. He was a great man and a good scientist. We happily remember his humor, insight, and endless energy. He will deeply be missed by all those privileged to have known this extraordinary man who greatly enriched our lives.

There is no doubt that prof. Haman would have contributed towards further advancing scientific research and education in his country which he dearly loved.

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